

Correlations between egg masses and plant height and tiller density were positive and significant. Taller and denser canopies were more preferred for egg deposition. BR4112-2B-6 was least preferred, probably because it had the shortest plants and produced fewer tillers (Table 2).

Leaf blade width and foliage color had no apparent influence on egg deposition. ■

Table 2. Yellow stem borer egg masses deposited on deepwater rice entries in a nethouse. Pot study, BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1989.

Entry	Reaction ^a in 1988	Plant height (cm)	Tiller density (no./pot)	Egg mass density (no./pot) ^b
Sadapankaich-HR40	HP	73.5	31.3	6.5 a
DWC-B-184	LP	67.0	26.4	5.1 ab
BR4112-2B-5	HP	62.5	21.2	4.0 ab
Habiganj Aman II	LP	54.6	27.2	2.9 b
BR4112-2B-6	LP	46.4	17.4	2.1 b

^a LP = less preferred, HP = highly preferred in the field. ^b Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Red stripe, a newly reported disease of rice in Vietnam

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A new disease on rice in the Mekong Delta has the typical symptom of an orange stripe extending from both ends of an oval lesion (Fig. 1).

The lesion usually begins as a small water-soaked yellow spot 0.1-0.3 cm in size. It gradually turns orange-red within 2-3 d. The stripe develops from both ends of the spot, enlarging rapidly under moist, hot conditions, and may extend the entire length of the leaf. Numerous stripes may occur on the same leaf. An infected leaf may die and dry out. Red stripe was also observed on the leaf

sheath. In severe cases, the entire plant may be killed 10-15 d before harvest.

Although the disease has been found on 20-d-old seedlings, it normally is most severe after heading, and can cause 50% yield reduction.

Red stripe was first observed in 1988, when thousands of hectares of rice were affected in Tien Giang Province. Since then, it has been readily found. In the 1990 summer and autumn season, thousands of hectares were affected by the disease. Most promising short-

duration varieties, such as IR64, IR66, IR19660, IR42, MTL 61, and MTL 58, were severely affected.

We isolated *Curvularia lunata* on PDA by culturing 0.1-0.3 cm leaf pieces cut from new spots. We obtained 65-75% fungus 3 to 5 d after culturing.

Inoculum was prepared from cultures grown in the same medium. We inoculated 35- to 45-d-old seedlings by spraying. Inoculated plants were placed in a moist chamber for incubation. Typical lesions appeared 7 d after incubation at 30-32°C, and 15 d after incubation at 26-28°C. Lesions developed on both 35- and 45-d-old seedlings.

When we sectioned diseased tissues, we observed abundant species and mycelium of *C. lunata* in the vascular systems (Fig. 2a,b). ■

1. Typical red stripe lesions on inoculated plants.

2. a) Conidia, conidiophores, mycelia of *C. lunata* PDA culture. b) Spores of *C. lunata* on PDA culture.

Correlations between light trap catches, field populations of yellow stem borer (YSB), and lunar phase

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As part of a larger study on the regional dynamics of rice insect pests, we examined the relationship between YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* catches in small kerosene light traps and populations in adjacent fields.

Nine traps were within a 17,000-ha area of uniform double cropping in Nueva Ecija Province, Philippines, during 1981 wet season. Near the median planting date of surrounding fields, experimental plots of IR52 were

planted within 150 m of the light traps. Egg masses counted on 200 plants at 4, 6, and 8 wk after transplanting (WT) were correlated significantly ($r = 0.69$, $P < 0.05$) with total number of female moths caught during the 3 mo the crop was standing. Percentage deadhearts (DH) at 4, 6, and 8 WT was correlated with total number of YSB males and females during the 3-mo period ($r = 0.75$, $P < 0.05$).

At seven of the sites, we monitored DH-weekly from 3 to 9 WT. The rate of change differed significantly among seven periods based on the lunar month (F_6 , $32 = 6.53$, $P < 0.01$), with the peak occurring 24-27 d after the full moon (Fig. 1). The number of egg masses and male and female moths caught in light traps also differed among the 7 periods (F_6 , $70 = 2.66$, $P < 0.02$; F_6 , $30 = 11.5$, $P < 0.01$; F_6 , $30 = 6.51$, $P < 0.01$, respectively).

The concentration of egg masses is particularly striking: the average in the 20-23 d period was greater than the total in other periods combined (Fig. 2).

Although the delay between maximum number of female moths and maximum

1. Rate of change per week of deadhearts in experimental fields in relation to lunar phase. Bars represent 1 standard error. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1981 wet season.

egg masses is longer than indicated by published descriptions of the YSB life cycle, the order of the peaks in number of females and eggs, and change in DH is as expected. The YSB generation length is substantially longer than that of a moth (45-55 d in the area studied), and it is unlikely that these peaks are due to synchronization of the insect's development with some external cue other than lunar phase.

2. YSB egg masses at 3 sampling occasions and catches in light traps over 3 mo in relation to lunar phase. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1981 wet season.

Similar trends were observed in the 1982 wet season. While wider confirmation is needed, these results suggest that scouting for damage caused by YSB should be done primarily in the 2 wk after the full moon. They also indicate that catches in small kerosene light traps do reflect patterns in the development of nearby field populations, lending support to the use of these traps in wide area monitoring of rice insect pests. ■

Virulence of brown planthopper (BPH) populations collected in China

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We monitored the virulence of BPH populations collected from Hainan, Guangdong, Guangxi, and Zhejiang Provinces in Apr-Jun 1987-90. Collected insects were mass-reared on susceptible variety TN1 and tested on resistant varieties IR26 (containing resistance gene *Bph 1*) and IR36 (*Bph 1 + bph 2*). IR26 and IR36 plants were transplanted at 1 plant/pot 30 d after sowing, and each pot caged with 10 5th-instar nymphs 15-30 d after transplanting. Surviving BPHs were counted 10 d after infestation.

BPH populations collected in 1987-88 had significantly lower survival on IR26 and IR36 than on TN1 (see table). The Zhejiang population had the lowest survival on variety IR26. Survival on

variety IR26 of BPH populations collected in 1989-90 was similar to that on susceptible check TN1. Survival on variety IR36 was still obviously lower than that on susceptible check TN1.

These results indicate the virulence of BPH populations was becoming strong

enough to damage varieties containing *Bph 1*. They also show that the BPH population was shifting from biotype 1 to biotype 2. Establishment of BPH populations on resistant varieties widely cultivated in China and field damage need further surveillance. ■

Survival of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål of different geographical populations on rice varieties. Hangzhou, China, 1987-90.

Locality	Date	Temperature (°C)	Survival (%) of 5th-instar nymphs		
			IR26	IR36	TN1
Hainan Lingshui	5-14 Sep 1987	24.9	45.0	19.0	66.0
Zhejiang Longyou			14.0	13.0	65.0
Guangdong Xinhui ^a	8-17 Sep 1987	28.8	44.0	12.0	82.0
Hainan Lingshui	5-14 Sep 1988	26.5	18.0	12.0	75.0
Zhejiang Longyou			9.0	3.0	88.0
Guangdong Xinhui ^a	26 Sep-5 Oct 1988	25.7	30.0	14.0	54.0
Hainan Lingshui	3-12 Sep 1989	24.4	54.0	18.8	67.0
Zhejiang Longyou			53.0	3.0	75.0
Zhejiang Hangzhou			55.0	10.0	62.0
Guangdong Xinhui ^a			46.0	4.2	64.0
Hainan Lingyou	30 Jun-10 Jul 1990	28.8	72.2	12.2	73.3
Guangxi Nanning	7-16 Jul 1990	30.2	65.6	7.8	64.4
Guangxi Longzhou			63.3	20.0	66.7
Zhejiang Longyou			71.1	12.2	73.3
Zhejiang Hangzhou			72.6	12.0	74.2

^aTested in Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Guangzhou, China.